

FOOD SYSTEMS IN UKRAINE: POST-WAR RECOVERY AND ENSURE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

International scientific and
practical forum

15-16 May 2024

Kharkiv
SBTU
2024

**Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine
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FOOD SYSTEMS IN UKRAINE: POST-WAR RECOVERY AND ENSURE
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: Scientific Papers of the International
Scientific and Practical Forum, 15-16 May 2024 / SBTU. Kharkiv, 2024. 56 p.
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14633006](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14633006)

WELCOME ADDRESS AT THE OPENING OF THE INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL FORUM

Andrii ODARCHENKO,
*People's Deputy of Ukraine, Chairman of the
Academic Council of State Biotechnological
University, Dr.Sc. (in Technics), Professor*

Good morning, dear friends, dear colleagues and attendees!
I would like to welcome everyone to our forum 'FOOD SYSTEMS OF UKRAINE: POST-WAR RECOVERY AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT'. At the beginning, I would like to say a deep word of gratitude to the Armed Forces of Ukraine for the opportunity to hold this event, even though it is online. It is because of their heroic actions that we are able to live in our native land and work for the sake of Ukraine!

I would like to take this opportunity to congratulate the staff and the community of Ukraine on the third anniversary of the establishment of the State Biotechnological University. Three years ago, everyone was worried about the future of the newly created institution. And we have overcome everything and become one of the most successful multidisciplinary institutions in the country. And even despite the war, we remain so. During these difficult three years, we have done the incredible. We have created a large-scale team of wonderful sincere people who are working for Ukraine!

I am grateful to my colleagues for supporting my initiative to hold the forum and to the participants who are also working on ways to solve current issues. Together with the university community and the authorities at all levels, we are planning how we can best contribute to the victory and development of the state. Through constant dialogue, we discuss, analyse and compare the achievements of international institutions that have common vectors of activity with the university. Once again, I see that the team has similar opinions on the assessment of our potential and development opportunities. Once again, I emphasise the need to consolidate stakeholders (politicians,

government agencies, foreign partners) around the spread of understanding, the need to create a single chain - practitioner, science, manufacturer. This will lead to the introduction of commissioned scientific developments into production. The European Union has opened accession negotiations for Ukraine. The format of the forum is based on the key aspects of the 'farm to table' concept. The principles of this concept have been implemented in the European Union and are being implemented on a large scale in Ukraine. Today, Ukraine has sufficient potential for accelerated development of activities in priority scientific areas and can become a headliner of scientific transformations!

I am confident that after productive dialogues on seven platforms within the forum, we will come up with a number of proposals and decisions on ways to post-war recovery and ensure sustainable development of the national food system. I would like to thank every scientist and employee for their uninterrupted research and fulfilment of their professional duties despite all the difficulties. Thank you, together to Victory! Glory to Ukraine!

Andrii KUDRYASHOV,
*Acting Rector of State Biotechnological University,
PhD in Technics*

Dear colleagues, guests and attendees!

I am glad to welcome you to the international scientific and practical forum co-organised by the staff of the State Biotechnological University! The university community not only supports centuries-old traditions, but also creates new ones. The traditions of BIOTECH!

Traditionally, in this hall, we congratulate the staff of SBTU on the day of the university's foundation and Science Day and recognise the best employees and scientists.

Today, we have the opportunity to work and stay in our home institution thanks to the courageous Security and Defence Forces of

Ukraine. Our employees and students are also in their ranks. We will always be eternally grateful to them and remember their heroism!

We have the opportunity to hold this event thanks to you, the staff of the State Biotechnological University. You are the ones who keep the educational and scientific frontline going. Despite the alarms and explosions, distances and constant blackouts, it is you who ensure the life of the university. Thank you for your attitude and understanding, your feedback and your relentless desire to move forward despite the difficulties. I continue to be amazed and proud of your decisions and actions, the ways you solve urgent problems. From providing basic working conditions and land cultivation to the forms of education, research and PhD defence. From organising help for fellow countrymen to collective support and donations to our heroic soldiers. We are grateful to you for supporting the vision of the university's management for the further development of the university. We are grateful for not standing aside, but outlining the problems that we do not always see. We are grateful for the collective solution of issues. This is how a real team works. Over the three years of our existence, we have really become more than just a team - a well-coordinated, strong, courageous and sometimes creative one. We really have a mutual connection. From the chairman of the academic council, vice-rectors to postgraduate students and applicants. In my opinion, we have become a full-fledged family. I believe that this trend of joint and effective work will continue in the future.

This year, another good tradition is joining the BIOTECH customs - the organisation and holding of an international scientific and practical forum. Its name and the issues that will be raised today and the ways to solve them are once again a confirmation of the relentless movement forward, development and faith in the future of the university, Kharkiv and Ukraine. I hope that this custom will also enter the walls of the university and become one of the hallmarks of our institution.

I wish the university staff, invited guests of the forum and the audience health, peaceful skies, goodness and tranquility, faith in the bright future of our unbreakable Ukraine!

Vivat BIOTECH! Glory to Ukraine!

PLENARY PRESENTATIONS

DIRECTIONS FOR STABILIZING UKRAINE'S FOOD SYSTEMS

*Yatsun L., Dr.Sc. (in Economics), Professor,
State Biotechnological University*

Ukraine's food systems are a significant source of value creation. Large areas of fertile black soil and the country's favorable landscape significantly impact its agricultural productivity. Agricultural land covers over 41 million hectares, or 70% of the country's territory. In 2021, Ukraine's agricultural sector accounted for approximately 11% of the country's GDP, 40% of exports, and 17% of officially employed labor force. From 1992 to 2020, Ukraine's grain production nearly doubled, and exports increased by 43.2 times, making Ukraine a major player in the agricultural sector (State Statistics Service, 2022). In 2022, Ukraine contributed 10% of global wheat exports and 50% of global sunflower oil exports (FAOSTAT, 2022). Agriculture also provided a livelihood for about 12 million Ukrainians living in rural areas before the war.

The war with Russia has caused significant damage and greatly impacted the agricultural sector. In 2022, the sector saw a 30% decrease in total production with a projected further reduction in sown areas by 25% in 2023 (compared to 2021). Livestock production decreased by 10%. The sector was also affected by shelling of energy infrastructure, leading to a nearly 12% reduction in production. Direct losses include damage to machinery and equipment, loss of ready products, harm to storage facilities, reduction in livestock numbers, damage to perennial crops like orchards, and theft or destruction of resources such as agrochemicals and fuel. The most affected were the physical infrastructure and lands in the eastern and southern regions, where the main military actions took place.

Ukraine's Recovery Plan and other documents outline three stages of post-war recovery for food systems. The first stage, in 2022, aimed to preserve the economic potential of the agro-industrial complex through the following measures: 1) ensuring food security by canceling certain taxes, simplified regulations, financial support for agribusiness; 2) creating new supply routes, increasing exports, and optimizing internal logistics.

The goal of the second stage (2023-2025) is to restore the economic potential of the agro-industrial complex to pre-war levels and attract investments in agriculture, especially in infrastructure. This stage involves various mechanisms to stimulate private investment, maintaining population purchasing power by reducing VAT on food, "de-shadowing" agricultural production (bringing the shadow economy of food production into the official sector and registering all producers as market operators), developing cooperative systems, diversifying material and technical support, and land reclamation.

The third stage (2026-2032) envisages measures aimed at enhancing the economic efficiency of agribusiness, diversifying export risks, and radically improving land use efficiency. It includes measures such as promoting the processing of agricultural raw materials (especially grains and oilseeds), building seed factories, supporting domestic production of agricultural machinery and equipment, developing transportation via the Danube River for access to European markets, supporting organic farming, complying with the EU Green Deal requirements, and aligning Ukrainian agricultural policy with the EU-Ukraine Association Agreement.

The recovery and stabilization of Ukraine's food systems are supported by both internal and external sources in various directions, involving government and international organizations, the agro-food business, farmers, and other stakeholders.

An important direction for supporting Ukraine's food systems is the activity of *the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations*. FAO's activities can be divided into five priority areas: 1) eradicating hunger, fighting food insecurity and malnutrition; 2) increasing productivity and stability in agriculture, forestry, and fisheries; 3) reducing poverty in rural areas; 4) assisting in creating safe and efficient agri-food systems, supporting small producers; 5) increasing the resilience of agricultural systems to threats and crises (natural disasters, anthropogenic catastrophes). Throughout its existence, FAO has launched numerous programs and projects that align with these priorities.

Ukraine actively cooperates with FAO, whose mission is to combat hunger worldwide. However, due to the war initiated by Russia, Ukraine needs help today. FAO provides this assistance by implementing programs to support Ukrainian farmers in cooperation

with the government. The approval of the Agreement and the establishment of an FAO office in Ukraine elevate the cooperation to a much higher level, including programs supporting agricultural producers and providing humanitarian assistance to Ukrainians in difficult circumstances. Closer coordination on grain export issues is expanding. Ukraine will continue to help countries facing food security issues. In the long run, this cooperation will contribute to the growth of Ukrainian exports and achieving the main goal – creating an export-oriented economy with high added value.

Interaction with the organization is carried out under the Ukraine-FAO Framework Cooperation Program. Projects implemented within its framework have made a significant contribution to shaping the policy of agricultural and rural development in Ukraine, increasing the capacity of the national phytosanitary certification system, providing agricultural advisory services, improving access to export markets, developing agricultural cooperatives, and enhancing the quality and safety of products.

The organization's work in Ukraine focuses on three priority areas through various technical cooperation projects:

Conservation and rational use of natural resources (agricultural land, forests, and water bodies);

Improving policies and programs in agricultural and rural development, considering Ukraine's role in ensuring regional and global food security;

Developing and strengthening production and marketing chains.

With the onset of Russia's large-scale invasion, FAO updated its Rapid Response Plan in Ukraine to assist small Ukrainian farmers and medium-sized producers, providing emergency agricultural aid (seeds, multipurpose cash assistance) to 80,000 people in 13 regions of Ukraine.

With financial support, FAO, in cooperation with the Ukrainian government, implements a grain storage support strategy, aiming to assist farmers with temporary storage solutions for their harvest and maintaining Ukraine's high export potential. The strategy includes

supplying Ukrainian farmers with grain storage bags, loading and unloading equipment, and modular grain storage facilities.

Ukraine is a member of most technical committees and statutory commissions of FAO (committees on agriculture, raw material market issues, forestry, Phytosanitary Commission, Commission on Genetic Resources, Codex Alimentarius Commission, etc.) and a party to several conventions. This underscores the importance of systematic participation by representatives of state authorities, associations, experts, and Ukrainian specialists in their activities. In 2021, Ukraine became a member of the Committee on World Food Security, an international platform for inclusive intergovernmental dialogue on key food security and nutrition issues.

Ukraine's food systems are also supported by the World Food Program (WFP), the largest humanitarian agency addressing hunger globally and promoting food security. WFP supports national and regional efforts to ensure food security, including for the poorest and most vulnerable children, women, and men. To achieve this goal, the program collaborates with various partners such as governments, UN agencies, non-governmental and international organizations, civil society, and the private sector. For its efforts in fighting hunger, contributing to improving conditions for peace in conflict-affected areas, and preventing the use of hunger as a weapon during wars and conflicts, the WFP received the Nobel Peace Prize in 2020.

Through interaction with WFP, Ukraine has opportunities for more active foreign economic activity and increasing export activities of Ukrainian manufacturing companies. There is significant potential for Ukrainian companies to participate in tenders for the procurement of goods for international humanitarian projects of WFP, which annually purchases various goods and services, primarily food, worth up to \$4 billion as part of the electronic system "UN Global Marketplace."

FAO's Rapid Response Plan for Ukraine in 2023 outlined three main areas of activity with funding exceeding \$200 million. The measures included:

Restoring food security and ensuring food independence for half a million rural households along the front line and in significantly affected areas through the provision of seeds, feed, and cash assistance;

Restoring critical food value chains through the provision of diesel and gas generators, seeds of wheat, barley, oats, and peas, temporary and long-term modular grain storage, and meeting other needs;

Strengthening critical elements of the agri-food system by enhancing capacities in testing and certification of alternative grain export routes, restoring veterinary services, partnering with specialized organizations to facilitate demining agricultural lands, and assessing damages and losses.

FAO's plan for Ukraine in 2024 envisions increasing activities in these areas in various forms – from summarizing innovations, statistics, and training to providing financial and technical assistance in critical points and elements of food systems.

Based on FAO experts' assessment of the current state of Ukraine's food systems (food production and supply chain), the following conclusions can be drawn to form a strategy for developing sectors and industries of food production, processing, and trade to insure risks and counter potential threats.

Significant strategic advantages of Ukraine, due to its natural resources, geographic location, and quality human capital, can form the basis for rapid economic growth in the agro-food sector. The mission of targeted programs for post-war recovery and sustainable development of food systems should be to create opportunities for ensuring adequate well-being, self-sufficiency, food security, and healthy nutrition for Ukrainian citizens through innovative, forward-looking economic growth of the agro-food chain. Ukraine can become a center of food security, a global leader in supplying high-value-added food products.

The strategic goals of post-war recovery and sustainable development of Ukraine's food systems should aim to solve the following tasks:

- Ensuring quality infrastructure (land, irrigation systems, finance, education and science, transport, storage facilities);
- Providing food producers with sufficient and accessible material and technical resources;

- Balancing the production of high and low-margin products to increase the profitability of the agro-food chain sectors;
- Promoting the development and full functioning of agricultural raw material processing; optimizing product sales in domestic and foreign markets;

- Ensuring mutually beneficial trade with countries worldwide and expanding access to external markets;
- Increasing the competitiveness of Ukrainian goods and services, creating a positive image of Ukraine, and ensuring the presence of Ukrainian producers in international markets;

- Implementing a balanced import policy regarding food, primarily stimulating investment rather than consumer imports;

- Creating a competitive creative economy for balanced development and promotion of Ukrainian food brands in international markets;

- Stimulating the development of entrepreneurial culture and competencies in the agro-industrial complex;

- Encouraging innovation in the agri-food chain sectors, integrating science, education, and business.

STRATEGY OF THE NATIONAL AGRI-FOOD COMPLEX IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE EUROPEAN AGRICULTURAL AND BIO- ENERGY MARKETS

*Bezuglyi M., Dr.Sc. (in Agricultural), Professor, Royal Member
National Academy of Agrarian Sciences of Ukraine, State
Biotechnological University*

The chairman introduced me as the author of several national programs of the agri-food complex (AFC) of Ukraine. Some of them, such as the grain production program, have already given their results, and some of them, such as the land reform, are still in the formative stage. Therefore, based on my own experience, I offer your attention my own vision for the restoration and further development of the food systems of our country.

Among the large number of tasks that the Ukrainian AFC will have to solve after the victory, we underline 5 main ones. First, we briefly characterize each of the strategic directions, and then we consider them in more detail.

1. Food security is, of course, the task No.1, defined by the Law of Ukraine "On the Basic Principles of State Agrarian Policy" and detailed in the Law "On Food Security of Ukraine". It should be reminded that these laws define food security as a socio-economic situation in the state, in which all its citizens are stably and guaranteed to be provided with food in the required quantity, assortment and appropriate quality.
2. Agricultural products of plant origin, produced in volumes that exceed the need for food security, are exported in the form of raw materials with minimal added value. Therefore, it is important to reorient our food systems towards the manufacturing of products with high added value. Ukraine should not be the "granary" of Europe, exporting grain and seeds of oil and leguminous crops, but the "bread-giving" of Europeans with Ukrainian food products.
3. The agricultural potential of Ukraine is determined by the possibility of using advanced agri-food and bioenergy biotechnologies, modern selection and genetic achievements in plant and animal breeding, the latest technologies for growing agricultural crops and the production

of livestock products, and deepening the level of processing of raw materials, which will allow doubling the gross domestic product compared to the pre-war level for 7 peaceful years after the victory.

4. The European Union has defined a strategy for the operation of food systems and the development of rural areas, which has three equal components: food security, development of green energy and environmental protection. Ukraine purposefully moves towards joining the EU, and therefore the development of its agri-food and bioenergy markets should become an important element of the state's agrarian policy.

5. Taking advantage of the presence of FAO representatives, your attention will be brought to our proposal regarding the more effective use of the agricultural potential of Ukraine in the fight against hunger in the world.

Let's move on to a more detailed analysis of each of these 5 directions. The basis of the further development of the national AFC is the production of grain, oil and leguminous crops as the main raw material resource of the industry. You can see the dynamics of the production of these crops in figures 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Gross harvest of grain in Ukraine

Fig. 2. Gross harvest of sunflower, rapeseed and soybeans in Ukraine

In 2021, their total production reached 100 million tons: 86 million tons of grain and 24 million tons of oil and leguminous crops. These production volumes were substantiated 13 years ago and were used as a basis of relevant state programs (M.D. Bezugliy et al., 2010, 2011). The majority of the grain harvest (75-80%) and more than 90% of oil and leguminous crops (except sunflower) are exported as raw materials with minimal added value. A pleasant exception in this list is sunflower seeds, 85% of which are processed in Ukraine. By the way, it should be reminded that such a high level of processing was achieved due to the state program that started work in Ukraine in 2023 and have produced relevant results for 8 years. As a result of the temporary occupation of part of the territory of Ukraine, a decrease in the intensity of production and problems with exports, the volume of grain production decreased in 2022-2023. Our forecast for the current year is more pessimistic, according to which grain production may fall below 50 million tons. However, despite this temporary fact, the strategy development should be based on the indicated volumes of production in the pre-war years with further consideration of the increase in productivity. The potential of the AFC using all agricultural land in the state is 130 million tons, including 100 million tons of grain and 30 million tons of oilseeds and legumes. Such volumes of production were substantiated by us at the previous forum of DBTU in 2021.

A prerequisite for balanced development of Ukraine's food systems is the development of animal breeding, because this industry is the main consumer of fodder grain and its processing products. We analyze this topic in detail at our sectional sessions. Now, we offer general information about the state of the industry (Fig. 3, 4).

Fig. 3. Cow population and milk production in Ukraine

Fig. 4. Pig population and meat production in Ukraine

It is an obvious fact that animal breeding in Ukraine clearly lags behind the needs of the industry. It does not provide even the minimum consumption standards for most animal products, except for poultry meat and eggs.

The task of increasing the added value can be solved by processing raw materials in Ukraine. There are three main directions of use of plant raw materials:

1. Production of compound feed for domestic animal breeding and poultry farming, as well as for export. If we bring the production of milk and all types of meat to the level of scientifically based consumption norms, it needs to produce 10 million tons of compound feed for additional animal breeding. This way of developing animal breeding will increase the added value of the used grain feed by 5-10 times and create 350,000 new jobs.

2. Industrial processing of grain and oil crops is the second direction of using plant products. All developed countries, including the EU, implement biofuel production programs from renewable energy

sources. A relatively new direction is the production of biopolymers that successfully replace polyethylene and polypropylene. But unlike synthetic polymers, which have a half-life of 500 to 1000 years, biopolymers are transformed into organic fertilizers by soil microorganisms in 2-3 months. The most vivid example of complex processing of corn grain is the USA, where more than half of the 380 million tons is used for industrial processing, 130 million tons are used for human consumption and animal feed, and only 50-60 million tons (13-16%) are exported. Industrial processing of grain and oil crops is limited in Ukraine and uses less than 1 million tons of raw materials. The law on the mandatory use of bioethanol was adopted in 2012 and unjustifiably repealed in 2014. After that, no government of Ukraine returned to this topic. Among oil crops, only sunflower seeds are successfully processed and then, mainly, to the crude oil, of which 4.5 million tons are exported every year. Deeper processing is very limited and does not exceed 10% of the volume of sunflower oil. Almost all rapeseed (about 4 million tons) and soybeans (almost 5 million tons) are exported in unprocessed form.

To process all the raw materials that are not used for the production of food products, then we need to build such a number of factories, as indicated on figure 5. Half a million jobs will be created at these 80-100 factories. The level of added value in industrial processing increases in 10 or more times.

Fig. 5. Number of enterprises required for industrial processing of agricultural raw materials

It is important to note that bioethanol and biopolymers are synthesized from grain carbohydrates, while oils are synthesized from fatty acids of oil crops. Processing products, such as meal, dry bard, etc., which are up 30-40% of the volume of raw materials, contain up to 40% protein and are high-quality ingredients for compound feed. This is again about animal breeding.

3. The third direction of using food grains can be the creation of a strategic stock of wheat, sorghum and other crops under the auspices of the UN. In our opinion, the strategic stock of food grains should always be at the disposal of FAO for a timely response to natural, social or political challenges that may lead to hunger in certain regions of the planet. The availability of such stock will significantly increase the stability and effectiveness of UN aid to countries suffering from hunger or malnutrition. Of course, the functioning of such stock will require replenishment to compensate for used grain and renewal of unused grain balances every year. We propose to build 100 elevators in the southern regions of Ukraine near seaports. By the way, these regions themselves are the main producers of food grain in Ukraine, which will reduce logistics costs for accumulating the necessary amount of grain. Regardless of the course of military operations, decision-making by the political leadership of Ukraine and negotiations with the FAO are possible now, because the implementation of such a project requires long-term diplomatic work.

The strategy proposed for the national AFC, like any other strategy, requires the development of an appropriate system of measures for its implementation. From another point of view, each of the proposed areas need a separate program. What it should be in the animal breeding, we will discuss on our sectional session. In this speech, let's underline some general suggestions, which would be useful for our colleagues.

The recommendations of some Ukrainian politicians regarding the complete liberalization of the agricultural market, when the "free market" itself regulates everything, are erroneous. There is not a single developed country in the world where food systems are regulated only by market relations. The examples of countries with outstanding achievements in AFC confirm that the programs must ensure: state regulation of the range and volume of production, stimulation of the development of certain industries, pricing of products, sustainable development of rural areas. The most striking examples of such programs are: 1) the US Agricultural Adjustment Act, which has been in effect since the Great Depression in the 1930s and which specifies the parameters of the industry's development every 6 years; 2) 25-year program for the development of China's agri-food complex, during the implementation of which the country achieved a certain level of food security in 2022, while 40 years ago people in some regions suffered from malnutrition and hunger. Due to this program,

grain production increased 3.5 times from 200 million tons in the 80s to a record 700 million tons, which will be obtained this year.

The development of a system of measures regarding Ukraine's entry into the EU should take into account future changes in the agri-food and bioenergy markets of Europe. I would like to pay special attention to the following two questions, which are not analyzed either by agricultural science or by the relevant bodies of the central government. On June 13, 2023, after long discussions, the European Parliament adopted a law on the removal of at least 20% of arable land from agricultural production. These areas, which in absolute terms are 20 million hectares of arable land, will be returned to natural biogeocenoses through afforestation and other environmental protection measures. Nature protection in Europe is becoming equivalent to business, that is extremely good news! But there is no doubt that a 20% reduction in agricultural land will be accompanied by a significant redistribution of agricultural and food flows. Ukraine can get a unique chance to enter the EU agri-food market if we offer favorable proposals. We have 1-1.5 years for this.

The second factor, which is favorable for Ukraine, is the lagging behind the countries of the European Union in the use of fuel from renewable sources. With plans to have 10% bioethanol in gasoline and 10% biodiesel in diesel fuel as early as 2022, the amount of biofuel is about 7% in 2024. The main reason for the lag, in our point of view, is the shortage of raw materials for processing. Another great opportunity for the Ukrainian AFC.

The purpose of my report was to show the role of science in the development of appropriate programs for the restoration and further development of Ukraine's food systems. I hope that such issues will be discussed on the sectional session of our forum and will be continued in further developments of Ukrainian scientists. I want to end the report with the slogan of one of the first national programs for the development of our AFC: "Prosperity through agrarian development of Ukraine!"

TRANSFORMATION OF FOOD SYSTEMS: IMPERATIVES OF RESILIENCE FOR UKRAINE¹

*Savytska N., Dr.Sc. (in Economics), Professor,
State Biotechnological University*

Food systems permeate every aspect of human existence, as food has exceptional political, economic, and social significance for any society. The categorical definition of "food system" has changed with the development of science, under the pressure of new challenges in the modern BANI world (brittle, anxious, nonlinear, incomprehensible), hybrid threats, and unpredictable shocks to the economy.

Source: F2F (2020). Farm to Fork Strategy. For a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system

In 2021, at the 42nd session of the FAO conference, the understanding of the concept of a food system was expanded. The food system includes, in addition to the cultivation of agricultural products, natural resources, food processing, wholesale and retail food trade, the hotel business, food services, recycling, as well as activities and processes related to non-food agricultural products (such as forestry, biofuels, biofibers, etc.), which are interconnected with food products for human consumption (FAO, 2021).

¹ This publication has been prepared as part of the planned scientific theme of the State Biotechnological University (0123U100365) "Marketing Management of Business Development Based on the Resilience of Socio-Economic Systems".

According to the European Commission, a food system includes the entire spectrum of actors and their activities involved in the production, storage, processing, distribution, trade, consumption, and disposal of food originating from agriculture (including livestock), forestry, fisheries, and aquaculture, the food industry, as well as the broader economic, social, and natural environment in which they are embedded (F2F, 2020).

In 2022, the European Commission announced a proposal to regulate the sustainability of food systems. The EU initiative aims to integrate sustainability policy into the overall EU policy related to food. The focus is on implementing the "Farm to Fork" Strategy, which lies at the heart of the European Green Deal and aims to address the challenges of sustainable food systems. The strategy aims to accelerate the green transition and ensure that not only food produced in the EU but also that supplied to the EU market is more sustainable. This indicates the introduction of an integrated food system approach, a fundamentally new concept of a sustainable food system (FSFS), which demonstrates the inseparable connections between human health, a healthy society, and a healthy planet.

The security of food systems also impacts human health, environmental condition, economic development, and culture. Modern food systems, by general assessment, consume 70% of natural water, cause the loss of 60% of biodiversity, and produce up to a third of greenhouse gas emissions. Food systems feed the planet's population – nearly 8 billion people – and also create jobs and livelihoods for 1 billion people. However, there is a dissonance where over 800 million people in the world are hungry, 2 billion suffer from micronutrient deficiencies, and 2 billion are overweight or obese (One Planet, 2022).

The growing world population, the negative impact of economic activity on the environment, climate change, globalization, economic inequality in income distribution, pandemics, and military conflicts all prompt the transformation of food systems worldwide.

The impulse of the UN Food Systems Summit (2021) brought together over 100 countries around the idea of transforming national food systems. Among these countries was Ukraine. In February 2022, a Presidential Decree launched the search for solutions to develop transformation priorities in areas such as healthy nutrition,

environmentally friendly production, resilience to market instability, and food accessibility for all population groups (DP of Ukraine, 2022).

The transformation of food systems is an ongoing process of changes woven into the fabric of global economic processes aimed at achieving priorities for sustainable economic development and ensuring the quality of life for current and future generations. After February 24, 2022, the main issues of transforming Ukraine's food systems concern resilience from the global to the micro-level.

The terminal challenges of Ukraine's food system include partial or complete destruction of agricultural enterprises, food production, and critical infrastructure; contamination of agricultural lands with heavy metals and mining; temporary occupation of some territories; destruction of irrigation systems in the southern regions due to the Kakhovka HPP explosion; and loss of human capital (KSE, 2022). This is not an exhaustive list. The war disrupted production and supply chains and exports, leading to increased logistics and production costs, inflation, and rising food prices worldwide. The cost of living crisis is a problem that, due to the unprovoked war in Ukraine, affects everyone globally. However, nearly 90% of Ukrainian small agricultural producers reported reduced incomes due to the war, and one in four reported ceasing or significantly reducing their agricultural activities. The total damage to our state's agriculture, according to experts, amounts to \$41.1 billion (WB, 2023).

Under new conditions, conventional intensive agricultural practices are not only environmentally but also economically impossible, as they become increasingly expensive and logistically challenging due to disrupted supply chains (Pylypenko, 2019), and under unstable wartime conditions, they may not bring predictable results.

According to the published "Rapid Damage and Needs Assessment" in February 2023, grain and oilseed production in Ukraine decreased by 37% in 2022. Nearly 90% of small agricultural producers surveyed by FAO in Ukraine reported reduced incomes due to the war, and one in four reported ceasing or significantly reducing their agricultural activities (FAO, 2023).

The full-scale invasion of Ukraine by Russia has tasked our society with preserving the socio-political and economic resilience of our state and has once again brought food security to the center of global priorities.

The imperative for the resilience of Ukraine's national food system is integration into the EU. In 2022, Ukraine received candidate status for EU membership. Starting in 2024, the screening (compliance assessment) of Ukrainian legislation with EU law has begun. Ukraine has made significant efforts and progress in legislation across many sections, including agriculture, rural development, food safety, veterinary, and phytosanitary policies. It has become clear that sustainable development issues under hybrid threats must be complemented by the resilience of any food system entity.

The resilience of food systems must become a priority for their transformation. Resilience is a multi-layered concept that includes not only financial and economic but also biological, energy, social, and behavioral criteria, among others. Fig. 1 shows the resilience pyramid of food systems.

Fig. 1. Resilience Pyramid of Food Systems

Source: Based on own study

In Fig. 1, market resilience includes of the:

1. primary food production sector (farms, livestock, fisheries, and other agricultural production);
2. secondary food production sector (transportation, processing, food packaging);
3. tertiary food production sector (wholesale and retail trade, hotel business, food services, tourism).

Resistance that is omnipresent. These are: consumer sector resilience (households, consumers: inclusiveness, consumption behavior models, diets, health, well-being); bioresource resilience (ecosystems and biodiversity); institutional resilience (regulators: local and state authorities and market self-regulators).

The essence of the transformation lies in achieving key goals (One Planet, 2022): easing the burden on the consumer and making sustainable, healthy food a simple and accessible product; easing the burden on the producer and ensuring fair incomes in the food chain; easing the burden on the planet from unsustainable food systems (One Planet, 2022).

Fig. 2. Directions for the Transformation of Food Systems

Source: Based on own study

The tasks facing global food systems, shown in Fig. 2, involve reorienting food and agricultural policy to ensure food security by restoring production capacity, supporting regenerative, durable, and economically adaptive systems in a changing planet, providing full and healthy nutrition, ensuring fair income throughout the food value chain: from cultivation, processing, packaging, consumption, and waste disposal.

The main tasks are as follows: overcoming two forms of malnutrition, both from food insufficiency and from the lack of access to quality and nutritious food; protecting the environment, including water resources, preventing biodiversity loss, and restoring biodiversity; preventing food losses and food waste; supporting small landowners

and family farms; developing economically viable and efficient value-added chains; mitigating the impacts of climate change and increasing the resilience of food systems to all shocks and hybrid threats; eliminating inequality in food systems, helping vulnerable populations access affordable healthy nutrition.

The transformation of food systems should occur at individual, local, national, and international levels. Producers and consumers must be able to adapt to sudden and unexpected changes in the market environment by developing resilience strategies. Transforming current food systems into sustainable and resilient ones requires radical changes in all elements of the food system: production, distribution, consumption, disposal, trade, and management. The transformation opportunities largely depend on the scale of increasing agricultural productivity by reducing the gap between actual and desired yields and changing the orientation of food production models from calorie-rich food to healthier and more nutritious food. So far, various innovations and investments have focused on measures to change incentives among producers. In current conditions, the consumer is seen as an agent of change in food systems. Investments in small and medium-sized local businesses in storage, processing, and retail trade will help provide new opportunities for circular production, distribution, and consumption of food.

The imperative of the European vision for the development of food systems is the implementation of the "F2F" Strategy, which contributes to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals outlined in the 2030 Agenda, particularly Goal 12 "Ensuring sustainable consumption and production patterns". Consumption and production are the foundation of any economic system (UN, 2015). The feature of the integrated EU FSFS strategy is not only regulating production models based on sustainable economic systems but also creating responsible consumption models that promote the formation of a healthy food environment and healthy diets. The main tools for transforming European and global food systems are research and innovation, digitalization, green investments, and breakthrough technologies for creating a circular bioeconomy, restoring biodiversity; ensuring transparency and traceability throughout the food chain; changing consumer culture and consumption patterns; and implementing the principles of One Planet – One Health.

Currently, the main issues concerning the transformation of Ukraine's food systems relate to strategic resilience. These include: measured integration into the EU, scientific and political interaction, and the development of inter-political dialogue. However, the European integration process is a two-way movement. Therefore, adaptation is required not only for Ukrainian policy but also for EU policy. The EU is undergoing a reform of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Key issues include budget allocation, discussions on the future of the European food system, farming, and Ukraine's place within it. Policy management changes must occur collectively, with the introduction of joint management at local, national, and international levels.

For Ukraine, overcoming the consequences of the war – pollution, demining, inflation, labor shortages – has already become everyday tasks, but accomplishing them without donor assistance is extremely difficult. The main imperatives are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Imperatives for the resilience of food systems in Ukraine

Source: Based on own study

Thus, creating a long-term food sovereignty strategy that includes the potential for forming protectionist policies and protecting national interests will allow Ukraine to maintain the competitiveness of its agricultural products in the markets of Asia, Africa, and the Middle East. It will also solidify the expansion into the EU market with organic products and reorient export policy from raw materials to the saturation of the single market with high value-added products.

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THE STATE OF SOIL AND PLANT RESOURCES IN AGRICULTURE AND THE FOREST SECTOR IN THE CONTEXT OF ENVIRONMENTAL CHANGES AND THE CONSEQUENCES OF MILITARY OPERATIONS

DISCUSSION PLATFORM № 1

DISCUSSION PLATFORM № 1

The state of soil and plant resources in agriculture and the forest sector in the context of environmental changes and the consequences of military operations

(Moderators: Doctor of Agriculture, Professor **Shevchenko M.V.**, Doctor of Economics, Professor **Koshkalda I.V.**)

1. «Features of modern farming systems under the influence of social, economic and environmental changes».

Shevchenko M.V., Doctor of Agriculture, Professor, State Biotechnological University.

2. « Ecological consequences of deforestation in Ukraine and ways to eliminate them in the post-war period ».

Raspopina S.P., Doctor of Agriculture, Associate Professor, Head of the Laboratory of Forest Soil Science, UkrNRILGA H.M. Vysotsky National Research Institute of Forestry; **Sedov A.O.**, senior lecturer, State Biotechnological University.

3. «The state of soil resources and the use of remote soil diagnostic methods during the survey of territories affected by military operations».

Gavva D.V., PhD in Agriculture, Associate Professor, **Krokhin S.V.**, PhD in Agriculture, Associate Professor, State Biotechnological University.

4. «Use of the gene pool of wheat species diversity in selection research at the Department of Genetics, Selection and Seed Production of the SBTU».

Rozhkov R.V., PhD in Biology, Associate Professor, State Biotechnological University.

5. «Methods of resource saving in intensive seed production technologies».

S.M. Dolya, Director of Agroexpert LLC.

6. «Conservation and enhancement of lands for recreational and nature protection purposes using forestry lands».

Glazunov O.V., deputy of the Oskil village council of Iziium district, Kharkiv region, chairman of the land commission.

7. «Ecological and technological aspects of post-war restoration of sloping lands».

Kolyada V.P., PhD in Agriculture, Senior Research Scientist, Head of the Laboratory of Soil Protection from Erosion and Remote Sensing Methods at the Sokolovsky National Research Centre of IGA.

8. «Monitoring the biodiversity of wild pollinating bees in agricultural landscapes and developing measures for their protection and efficient use in the north-east of Ukraine».

Filatov M.O., PhD in Agriculture, Associate Professor, **Lezhenina I.P.**, PhD in Agriculture, Associate Professor, State Biotechnological University.

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BIOTECHNOLOGICAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECTS OF THE RESTORATION AND FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF THE AGRI-FOOD SECTOR OF UKRAINE

DISCUSSION PLATFORM № 2

Biotechnological and environmental aspects of the restoration and further development of the agri-food sector of Ukraine

(Moderator - Doctor of Agriculture, Professor **I.V. Gnoevyi**)

1. «Stock breeding development is a prerequisite for increasing the added value of Ukraine's agri-food sector».

Bezuglyi M.D., Doctor of Agriculture, Professor, Academician of the National Academy of Agrarian Sciences of Ukraine, State Biotechnological University.

2. «The state and current problems of dairy farming in Ukraine».

Ruban S.Y., Doctor of Agriculture, Professor, Corresponding Member of NAAS, National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine.

3. «Impact of military operations on aquatic agroecosystems».

Rylskiy O.F., Doctor of Biology, Professor, Zaporizhzhia National University.

4. «Promoting safe agricultural production: choosing organic waste processing technologies in the post-war recovery».

Valetska O.V., PhD in Agriculture, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU).

5. «Problems, prospects and sustainable development of poultry farming».

Katerynych O.A., Doctor of Agriculture, Professor, State Experimental Poultry Station.

6. «Problems and challenges of wartime for the Ukrainian fishing industry».

Novitskiy R.O., Doctor of Agriculture, Professor, Dnipro State Agrarian and Economic University.

7. «Features of feeding high-productive cows in robotic milking systems».

Gnoevyi I.V., Doctor of Agriculture, Professor, State Biotechnological University.

8. «Restoration of dairy cattle in Ukraine using methods of modern biotechnology of reproduction».

Shcherbak O.V., PhD in Agriculture, Professor, State Biotechnological University.

9. «Molecular basis for the creation of sustainable forest plantations in Ukraine to replace those damaged by military operations».

Davydenko Kateryna, Doctor of Biology, PhD, Uppsala University of Agricultural Sciences, Uppsala, Sweden (Uppsala universitet).

10. «Breeding and technological programme for pig hybridisation».

Khokhlov A.M., Doctor of Agriculture, Professor, State Biotechnological University.

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BUILDING NATIONAL CAPACITY TO DEAL WITH PUBLIC HEALTH ISSUES IN THE CONTEXT OF 'ONE HEALTH'

DISCUSSION PLATFORM № 3

DISCUSSION PLATFORM № 3

Building national capacity to deal with public health issues in the context of 'One Health'

(Moderator – PhD in Veterinary, Associate Professor **O.O. Tsymerman**)

1. «Milk quality assessment criteria and their harmonisation with EU legislation».

Zhilina V.M., PhD in Veterinary , Associate Professor, State Biotechnological University.

2. «Resistance of milk microflora to antibiotics in the process of dairy products manufacturing».

Yakubchak O.M., Doctor of Veterinary , Professor, **Martynenko O.A.**, post graduate student,

Taran T.V., PhD in Veterinary, Associate Professor, National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine.

3. «The relevance of the problem of staphylococcal infections and antibiotic resistance: risks for companion animals and humans».

Garagula G.I., PhD in Veterinary, Associate Professor, State Biotechnological University.

4. «Ensuring the epizootic welfare of stockbreeding in Ukraine in relation to tuberculosis (experience of the IECVM)».

Paliy A.P., Doctor of Veterinary, Professor, Director of the IECVM.

5. «Ways to implement the latest technologies to ensure traceability in the food chain and crisis management».

Marchenkov M.V., Advisor to the Director of the Cyberport Research Institute, State Biotechnology University.

6. «Contemporary challenges and threats to the spread of zoonotic parasitoses in Ukraine».

Nikiforova O.V., PhD in Veterinary, Associate Professor, **Liulin P.V.**, PhD in Veterinary, Associate Professor, State Biotechnological University.

7. «Judicial examination of sausage products based on pre-trial investigation materials in criminal proceedings: problems and features».

Yatsenko I.V., Doctor of Veterinary , Professor, State Biotechnological University.

8. «Efficiency of probiotics use in broiler chickens to improve the gut microbiome».

Yakubchak O.M., Doctor of Veterinary, Professor, **Vivich A.Y.**, post graduate student, **Grib Y.V.**, PhD in Veterinary, Senior Lecturer, National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine.

9. «Controlling the incidence of mastitis in cows and evaluating the effectiveness of treatment measures».

Fedorenko S.Y., Doctor of Veterinary, Professor, State Biotechnological University.

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DISCUSSION PLATFORM № 4

SUSTAINABLE FOOD PROCESSING: THE PRESENT AND POST-WAR TRANSFORMATION

DISCUSSION PLATFORM № 4

Sustainable food processing: the present and post-war transformation

(Moderator - Doctor of Technics, Professor **T.M. Holovko**)

1. «The bakery industry: current state and post-war development prospects».

Samokhvalova O.V., PhD in Technics, Professor, **Oliynyk S.G.**, PhD, Professor, State Biotechnological University; **Tanaskova N.O.**, Director of R&D Department, Balex Group of Companies.

2. «Responsible consumption and production: realisation in new food generations».

Hrynchenko O.O., Doctor of Technics, Professor, **Foshchan A.L.**, Doctor of Technics, Professor, **Hrynchenko N.G.**, Doctor of Technics, Professor, **Radchenko A.E.**, PhD in Technics, Associate Professor, State Biotechnological University.

3. «Reducing food losses and food waste as a way to achieve a sustainable food system under wartime and post-war reconstruction».

Priss O.P., Doctor of Technics, Professor, Motornyi Tavria Agrotechnological University; **Evlash V.V.**, Doctor of Technics, Professor, State Biotechnological University; **Tovma L.F.**, PhD in Technics, Associate Professor, National Academy of the National Guard of Ukraine.

4. «Post-war restoration of the Ukrainian food industry by educators: training and retraining of specialists, development and improvement of technologies, support and maintenance of food business enterprises».

Pogarska V.V., Doctor of Technics, Professor, **Yurieva O.O.**, PhD in Technics, Associate Professor, **Pogarskyi O.S.**, PhD in Technics, Associate Professor, **Selutina G.A.**, PhD in Technics, Associate Professor, State Biotechnological University.

5. «Conceptual directions for improving the technology of glued intestinal films».

Mikhailov V.M., Doctor of Technics, Professor, **Onishchenko V.M.**, Doctor of Technics, Professor, **Park A.O.**, Doctor of Technics, Professor, **Yancheva M.O.**, Doctor of Technics, Professor, State Biotechnological University.

6. «Features of wheat grain typing and classification of milling products in Canada».

Shanina O.M., Doctor of Technics, Professor, State Biotechnological University; **Johnston A.T.**, PhD in Technics, Ardent Mills, Saskatoon, Canada.

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DEVELOPMENT OF MACHINE BUILDING IN THE POST-WAR PERIOD AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION IN UKRAINE

DISCUSSION PLATFORM № 5

Development of machine building in the post-war period and the development of agricultural production in Ukraine
(Moderator - Doctor of Technics, Professor **R.V. Antoshchenkov**)

1. «Prospects for the creation of a research and testing centre for energy efficient products».

Antoshchenkov R.V., Doctor of Technics, Professor, State Biotechnological University.

2. «Improving food security through the development of competitive technologies for obtaining high-quality seeds with improved biopotential».

Bredikhin V.V., PhD in Technics, Associate Professor, Dean of the Faculty of Mechatronics and Engineering, State Biotechnology University.

3. «Innovative resource-efficient equipment and technological solutions for processing plant raw materials into safe multifunctional products».

Mikhailov V.M., Doctor of Technics, Professor, **Zagorulko O.E.**, PhD in Technics, Associate Professor, **Zagorulko A.M.**, PhD in Technics, Associate Professor, State Biotechnological University.

4. «Production of fluoroplastic-4 products in Ukraine in the post-war period: analysis and solution strategies».

Kalyuzhnyi O.B., PhD in Technics, Associate Professor, State Biotechnological University; **Platkov V.Y.**, Doctor of Physics and Mathematics, Professor, Volodymyr Dahl East Ukrainian National University.

5. «Improving the environmental safety of domestic motor vehicles using advanced GHG neutralisation systems».

Manoilo V.M., Doctor of Technics, Associate Professor,
Makarenko M.G., Associate Professor, **Shevchenko I.O.**, PhD in
Technics, Associate Professor, State Biotechnological University;
Kozlov Y.Y., Associate researcher, Leonid Pogorelyi Ukrainian
Research Institute of Industrial Technology.

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**RELIABLE OPERATION OF
UKRAINE'S ENERGY
SECTOR IS A KEY FACTOR
IN THE EXISTENCE OF THE
NATIONAL ECONOMY**

DISCUSSION PLATFORM № 6

Reliable operation of Ukraine's energy sector is a key factor in the existence of the national economy

(Moderator - Doctor of Technics, Professor **O.O. Miroshnyk**)

1. «Development of local energy supply systems with different types of generation as a strategy to provide sustainable operation of agricultural enterprises in war time».

Moroz O.M., Doctor of Technics, Professor, State Biotechnological University; **Pavlov A.O.**, Engineer, Monolith Construction Company.

2. «Commissioning is an innovative approach to increasing the energy efficiency of buildings and enterprises in the wartime and post-war periods».

Klepanda O.S., Director of Insolar-Klimat LLC; **Miroshnyk O.O.**, Doctor of Technics, Professor, State Biotechnological University.

3. «Ensuring the sustainability of the refrigeration chain in the current energy and agricultural sector».

Potapov V.O., Doctor of Technics, Professor, **Petrenko O.V.**, PhD in Technics, Associate Professor, State Biotechnological University; **Anashkin S.V.**, Chairman of the Board, Director of the Refrigeration Association of Ukraine; **Smilik M.M.**, owner of MS Kholod LLC.

4. «Implementation of the main refrigeration tasks on the basis of modular decentralised systems».

Molskyi S.M., Engineer, category I, expert of the Refrigeration Association of Ukraine.

5. «Introduction of heat pumps in the food industry in Ukraine».

Knysh S.V., Technical Director of LICOND-ODESSA LLC; **Zheliba Y.O.**, PhD in Technics, Associate Professor, Odesa National Technological University, Director of NIO KHOLOD LLC; **Khmelniuk M.G.**, Doctor of Technics, Professor, Odesa National Technological University.

6. «Training of specialists of I, II and III levels of higher education at the Department of ERBME for the restoration and sustainable development of the food system of Ukraine».

Khandola Y.M., PhD in Technics, Associate Professor, **Lysychenko M.L.**, Doctor of Technics, Professor, State Biotechnological University.

7. «Animal and human cloning: achievements and prospects».

Shygimaga O.V., Doctor of Technics, Professor, State Biotechnological University.

FOOD SYSTEM TRANSFORMATION: CHALLENGES, OPPORTUNITIES, PRIORITIES

DISCUSSION PLATFORM № 7

DISCUSSION PLATFORM № 7

Food system transformation: challenges, opportunities, priorities

(Moderator - Doctor of Economics, Professor **Kashchena N.B.**)

1. **«Ukraine's agricultural sector at war: problems and prospects».**

Glyan T.I., Deputy Director of Agro-Glyan PE, post graduate student at the State Biotechnological University

2. **«Post-war realities of managing recovery and transformation to sustainable development of agri-food systems (on the example of LLC 'Gagarin Agrofirm»).**

Gatsko A.F., Doctor of Economics, Professor, Director of Gagarin Agrofirm LLC; **Sagachko Y.M.**, PhD in Economics, Associate Professor, **Gridin O.V.**, PhD in Economics, Associate Professor, State Biotechnological University.

3. **«Marketing innovations for sustainable and resilient food systems».**

Zhegus O.V., Doctor of Economics, Professor, State Biotechnological University.

4. **«Prospects for the Development of Entrepreneurship in Latvia and Ukraine in the Context of the European Green Deal Implementation».**

Iluta Arbidane, Doctor of Economics, Professor, Rezekne Academy of Technologies, Latvia; **Dmytro Odarchenko**, Doctor of Economics, Professor, State Biotechnological University; **Halyna Synytsyna**, PhD in Economics, Associate professor, State Biotechnological University; **Svetlana Sorokina**, PhD in Technics, Associate professor, State Biotechnological University, Ukraine.

5. **«European integration concept of ecological and economic synergy in the development of the food system of Ukraine».**

Bochulya T.V., Doctor of Economics, Professor, State Biotechnological University.

6. «Challenges of sustainable agri-food systems in Poland and Ukraine».

Savytska N., Dr.Sc. (in Economics), Professor, State Biotechnological University (Ukraine);

Malak-Rawlikowska A., Dr.hab., Professor, Warsaw University of Life Sciences (SGGW) (Poland).

7. «Green post-war recovery of Ukraine's food systems».

Kashchena N.B., PhD in Economics, Professor, Yancheva L.M., PhD, Professor, State Biotechnological University.

8. «Risks of large-scale privatisation of Ukraine's land stock in the context of food security».

Voroniansky O.V., PhD in History, Professor, State Biotechnological University.

9. «Transport and logistics support for the production and delivery of vegetables in the Kharkiv region».

Dmytro Muzyliov, PhD in Technics, Associate Professor, State Biotechnological University; **Sysenko I.I.**, PhD in Technics, General Director of Zmiiv Vegetable Factory.

10. «Optimising the timing of grain sales».

Lytvynov A.I., Doctor of Economics, Professor, State Biotechnological University.

11. «Responsible marketing to children in the food and drink market».

Lylyk I.V., PhD in Economics, Associate Professor, Vadym Hetman Kyiv National University, President of the Ukrainian Marketing Association; **Savytska N.L.**, Dr.Sc. in Economics, Professor, State Biotechnological University; **Prinko D.G.**, postgraduate student, Sumy State University.

12. «Ukrainian hospitality market under the war-time and its revitalisation».

Skrynnik V.I., PhD in Food Technology, State Biotechnological University.

13. «*Priority tourism destinations for sustainable development in Ukraine: current challenges*».

Khudaverdieva V.A. PhD in Economics, Associate Professor,
State Biotechnological University.

EXPLANATORY NOTE ON THE FORUM RESOLUTION

The National Recovery Council, established by the President of Ukraine, has presented a Recovery Plan for Ukraine² covering the period 2022-2032 and estimated at \$750 billion (excluding security and military spending). The plan consists of three phases - the war economy (2022), post-war recovery (2023-2025) and the new economy (2026-2032) - and includes 850 projects under 15 national programmes in various sectors of the economy and public life. As a result of the implementation of this plan, the Government of Ukraine intends to restore Ukraine as a strong European country focused on modernisation, continuing European integration reforms, introducing green technologies, ensuring the rule of law and increasing transparency and accountability throughout the recovery process. These intentions are reflected in the adopted Lugano Declaration, signed by the conference participants (5 July 2022).

On 21-22 June 2023, the second Ukraine Recovery Conference³ was held in London (UK). World leaders, together with international financial institutions, business representatives and civil society organisations, discussed the implementation of the Recovery and Development Plan for Ukraine and ways to mobilise international support for Ukraine's economic and social recovery, with a focus on private sector participation in the reconstruction process. The partners committed to provide around USD 60 billion of new financing in the short and medium term, of which EUR 50 billion is being provided by the European Commission (under the Ukrainian Facility) in the form of concessional loans, grants and confiscated assets of the Russian Federation.

The Recovery Plan for Ukraine includes more than ten national programmes. The Government of Ukraine will focus on five key areas in the near future, including agriculture. The New Agricultural Policy Working Group was established under the National Recovery Council and has developed a detailed business plan for the recovery of Ukraine's agricultural sector.

² <https://recovery.gov.ua/en>

³ <http://surl.li/ecnjzs>

Like the Ukraine Recovery Plan, the New Agricultural Policy⁴ is divided into three phases. The first phase, 2022, was aimed at preserving the economic potential of the agricultural sector through the following measures: 1) ensuring food security through the abolition of certain taxes, simplified regulation, and financial support for agribusiness; and 2) creating new supply routes, increasing exports, and optimising domestic logistics.

The goal of the second stage (2023-2025) is to restore the economic potential of the agricultural sector to pre-war levels and attract investment in agriculture, in particular in infrastructure. It envisages various mechanisms to stimulate private investment, preserve the purchasing power of the population by reducing the VAT rate on food, "detention" agricultural production (removing food production from the black economy and registering all producers as market operators), developing a system of cooperation and diversifying logistics and land reclamation.

The third stage (2026-2032) involves measures aimed at increasing the economic efficiency of agribusiness, diversifying export risks, and radically improving the efficiency of land use. It includes the following measures: stimulating the processing of agricultural raw materials (primarily grain and oilseeds), building seed plants, supporting domestic production of agricultural machinery and equipment, and developing transport on the Danube River to access markets in Central and Western Europe. This phase also includes support for organic agriculture, implementation of the EU Green Deal, and further alignment of Ukrainian agricultural policy with the EU-Ukraine Association Agreement.

The International Forum "Food Systems of Ukraine – Post-War Recovery and Sustainable Development" directs the scientific potential of SBTU to the implementation of the Recovery Plan of Ukraine (by stages), implementation and development of other decisions, as stated in the Forum Resolution.

⁴ <https://www.kmu.gov.ua/storage/app/sites/1/recoveryrada/ua/new-agrarian-policy.pdf>

**RESOLUTION
OF THE INTERNATIONAL FORUM
"FOOD SYSTEMS OF UKRAINE - POST-WAR RECOVERY
AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT"**

15-16 May 2024

Supporting the efforts of the scientific community and the important role of food systems in ensuring the democratisation of society and in promoting sustainable development; guided by the fact that FAO, the UN, the European Union have recognised their importance in providing the population with safe and quality food, food producers in Ukraine deserve a new policy of agro-food reconstruction that supports the traditional food culture based on the health of the nation, and in which environmental responsibility and economic justice take precedence over modern. Taking into account the above and having considered the reports and presentations at the Forum on strengthening the role of food systems during the war and post-war reconstruction of Ukraine, the participants of the Forum:

1. Underline that food systems in Ukraine can make a significant contribution to overcoming the interconnected crises caused by the war, both in agriculture, food chain sectors and in the economic, social, environmental and humanitarian spheres. To this end, the Forum participants recommend to create a Scientific and Public Platform for Food Systems Support in Ukraine (by sector) in accordance with the UN Global Action Plan, the FAO Framework Agreement, the Recovery Plan for Ukraine, the Ukraine Facility's Post-War Recovery Strategy, the Decisions of the President and Government of Ukraine and other decisions on the food systems development strategy.

2. Take note of the speeches made at the Forum by representatives of state and regional authorities, business, agricultural and rural development scientists, representatives of the FAO Office in Ukraine, international academic and political institutions on cooperation between these organisations, agricultural enterprises and food producers of Ukraine, scientific and educational institutions and intend to continue and deepen such cooperation.

3. Support the proposals of the Office of the President of Ukraine and the Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food of Ukraine to strengthen dialogue at all levels of Ukrainian government with agricultural

enterprises, food producers, research and education institutions and international organisations, to expand ways to promote cooperation on post-war recovery and sustainable development of food systems and its coordination with civil society.

4. Instruct the Organising Committee of the Forum, together with the Associations of Agribusiness, Farmers, Food Producers and research teams of relevant institutions of Ukraine, to facilitate the systematic monitoring and publication of materials on the implementation of decisions on the restoration and development of food systems, this resolution, strategies for post-war recovery and sustainable development of food systems on inter-sectoral platforms, in scientific publications and Internet resources of the Forum participants.

5. Address the authorities with a request to change the pre-war agri-food model of Ukraine, focused on raw material exports, soil and water depletion, and the exsanguination of rural lifestyles, to a targeted innovative and proactive strategy for the restoration and transformation of food systems, operating on the basis of sustainable development in accordance with EU policies, regulations and standards. To this purpose, it is proposed that the key institutions of state power consolidate efforts to implement the following immediate, medium-term and long-term measures: in the context of guaranteeing Ukrainians the constitutional right to affordable, high-quality and safe food of domestic production, to conduct an examination of agricultural legislation developed during the period and in wartime for its compliance with public needs, interests of agricultural enterprises, food producers, logistics, trade and other entities of the food chain, UN principles for the responsible management of land, forests and fisheries, and the basic principles of the EU Green Deal.

Appeal to international donor organisations for technical support; allocate a separate programme in the Recovery Plan for Ukraine to restore losses and build the capacity of various forms of agriculture; create a state institution for post-war rural recovery to build the capacity of food systems. In order to guarantee national security and preserve the territorial integrity of the state during the war and post-war reconstruction, delay the effect of the Laws of Ukraine and review the implementation of market transactions for the purchase and sale of agricultural land during the period of martial law until legal, organisational and financial mechanisms are established to protect the public interest and guarantee peasants, farmers and agricultural

producers real opportunities to purchase agricultural land; improve sectoral management of agricultural and rural development for capacity development, food systems and preservation of rural lifestyles, within the framework of institution-building and technical cooperation instruments between the EU and Ukraine, strengthen the representation of science, education, agri-food sector in government at all levels. To appeal to the Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO) for assistance in organising in Ukraine a broad awareness-raising and training of representatives of all levels of government, deputies and local self-government bodies on collectively developed international approaches and documents on promoting the development of food systems, namely: The UN and FAO global action plan, the UN Voluntary guidelines on the responsible governance of tenure of land, forests and fisheries, and the FAO principles for responsible investment in agriculture and food systems; to request the EU delegation in Ukraine to join the organisation of awareness-raising and training activities in Ukraine to raise awareness of government officials, deputies of all levels and local governments on the principles and approaches of the EU's Common Agricultural Policy, the European Green Deal and the practice of their application in agricultural and rural development, etc. within the framework of the existing instruments of institution-building and technical cooperation between the EU and Ukraine Twinning.

6. Intensify the participation of scientific teams in the development of targeted strategies for post-war recovery and sustainable development of food systems in Ukraine, in particular by initiating:

- The State Programme for Post-War Recovery and Sustainable Development of Agricultural Enterprises and Food Self-Sufficiency of Citizens for the period up to 2030, coordinated with the UN and FAO Global Action Plan in accordance with the basic principles of the EU Common Agricultural Policy (2023-2027);

- The state programme to support the production of domestic seed material and young farm animals to provide farms, peasant households and citizens with agricultural products for food self-sufficiency;

- A national programme for the transition to progressive agroecological management practices. To request international agro-ecological platforms to adapt agro-ecological models of commercial farming based on traditional environmentally safe approaches and

technologies for Ukraine, using domestic scientific developments and permaculture practices; to develop mechanisms for flexible assessment and compensation of losses (direct and indirect) from the war, taking into account the specifics and needs of food producers, and adapt these approaches in the post-war period to be incorporated into the agricultural policy system to respond to peacetime challenges (natural disasters, climate change, etc.);

- A state programme for de-mining, restoration of agricultural land, transferring it to other categories, withdrawal of some damaged agricultural land from circulation with the granting of appropriate compensation to its owners;

- A state programme for the formation of regional networks of local agricultural markets in the areas where agricultural products are grown, which ensure a short product supply chain, minimise the number of economic operators, and ensure close economic and social relations between producers and consumers. Promote the introduction of solidarity agriculture models and the development of diverse logistics systems to meet the needs of agricultural producers and consumers.

7. Actively use the results of domestic scientific research to restore agricultural land, in particular, on the feasibility of introducing state programmes to support the development of service cooperatives in rural areas to meet the needs of agricultural producers in the areas of agricultural marketing, finance and logistics. To substantiate the formation of a national network of agricultural credit cooperatives, taking into account EU practices, which will strengthen the position of agricultural producers in the financial and credit market.

8. Promote the implementation of EU Regulations that legalise support for food systems, regulatory frameworks and standards through awareness-raising activities among key stakeholders.

9. Recommend introducing a system of public procurement of agricultural products for public needs (schools, hospitals, the Armed Forces) from agricultural producers with an appropriate procurement quota for public needs. Simplify the conditions for small agricultural producers to participate in state sales channels.

10. Develop methodologies and conduct an All-Ukrainian agricultural census, make an inventory of economic entities and the land fund in the post-war period to inform the development of a scientifically based differentiated agricultural policy for different groups of producers and create favourable conditions for the development of an innovative agro-technological system.

11. The Academic Council of SBTU together with the Organising Committee of the Forum should prepare and consider the Plan for involving departments and research teams in the development of strategies and proposals for post-war recovery and sustainable development of Ukraine's food systems in the stages of wartime economy, post-war recovery and the New Agricultural Policy.

Scientific Papers

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